

THE ROLE OF THE TEACHER-APPRENTICES SCHOOL IN TRANSFERRING NATIONAL CRAFTS TRADITIONS TO GENERATIONS

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ANNOTATION: This article analyzes the role and importance of the master-apprentice school in passing on the traditions of national crafts to generations. The centuries-old experience of the Uzbek people in crafts, the stages of its formation, and traditional methods of teaching the secrets of the craft to the younger generation are highlighted. The pedagogical possibilities of the master-apprentice system in not only forming professional skills, but also in educating young people in the spirit of hard work, responsibility, patience, respect for national values, and patriotism are revealed. Also, effective ways to use the master-apprentice tradition in the modern education system, as well as current issues and prospects for preserving and developing the heritage of national crafts, are analyzed. Based on the results of the research, scientific and practical recommendations have been developed for instilling national crafts in the minds of young people and integrating them into the educational process.

KEY WORDS: national crafts, master-apprentice school, craft traditions, folk applied arts, vocational education, spiritual values, labor education, cultural heritage, craft training, pedagogical activity, youth education, national identity, craft schools, innovative education, continuing education.

INTRODUCTION

The spiritual and cultural development of each nation is closely related to its national values, customs and traditions formed over the centuries. One of such

invaluable heritages is national crafts. Crafts are a unique socio-cultural phenomenon that embodies the lifestyle, worldview, aesthetic taste and work culture of the people, and they serve as an important means of ensuring the spiritual connection between generations. In the centuries-old history of the Uzbek people, such types of crafts as pottery, jewelry, embroidery, coppersmithing, woodcarving, carpet weaving, and weaving have been formed and have become an integral part of the life of the people.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Historical sources testify that the territory of Central Asia has long developed as one of the centers of handicrafts. As a result of the interaction of cultures of different peoples along the Great Silk Road, new types and methods of handicrafts emerged. The handicraft schools formed in cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Kokand, Margilan, Rishton are known throughout the world for their artistic and practical significance. The products created in these schools not only satisfied economic needs, but were also valued as an important component of the spiritual wealth and cultural heritage of the people.

The role of the master-student tradition in the preservation and development of national crafts to this day is incomparable. This system has served for centuries as the most effective form of transmitting the secrets of the craft, professional experience and labor culture from one generation to another. The master instilled in his student not only the secrets of the craft, but also such qualities as decency, diligence, responsibility, humanity and respect for national values. Therefore, the master-student relationship has formed an integral part of national crafts and has ensured its continuous development.

In today's conditions of globalization and informatization, the issue of preserving the national cultural heritage and passing it on to the younger generation is becoming increasingly important. As a result of the widespread use of modern

technologies and new production methods, some traditional crafts are under threat of extinction. In such conditions, one of the important tasks is to effectively use the opportunities of the master-apprentice school, interest young people in national crafts, and integrate the experience of craftsmen into the educational process.

RESULTS

During the years of independence, a number of reforms have been implemented in our country aimed at developing national crafts, supporting craftsmen, and restoring the traditions of the master-apprenticeship. The expansion of the activities of craft centers, the improvement of the activities of the "Hunarmand" association, and the introduction of state programs for the orientation of young people to the profession are increasing the effectiveness of work in this area. This further strengthens the need for in-depth study of the pedagogical potential of the master-apprenticeship school and its use in the educational process.

From this perspective, the role of the master-apprentice school in transmitting national craft traditions to generations, its historical formation, pedagogical significance, and opportunities in the modern education system are of significant scientific and practical importance. This article analyzes the role of the master-apprentice system in the preservation and development of the national craft heritage, its impact on the education of young people, and its pedagogical aspects.

DISCUSSION

Handicraft products were initially produced in families, in small areas, based on the needs of the people of that settlement, and gradually the finished products were taken to the markets. This phenomenon gave impetus to the development of handicrafts as a separate, independent type of labor. The handicraft product brought to the market and whose value was determined automatically became a commodity and, as a result of the application of the principle of exchange in production, began to be exchanged for other products. Another factor that influenced the rapid

development of the industry was the specialization of the production of handicraft products, and the concentration of craftsmen in a certain point. Thus, neighborhoods of potters, blacksmiths, cradle makers, knife makers, tanners, saddlers, archers, beggars, etc. were formed.

At this point, without going into detail about the advantages of having a profession, as put forward in the sources and works mentioned above, we will highlight Kaykovus' views on this issue as an example.

The sixth chapter of the work "Qabusnama" created by Kaykovus is directly entitled "On the remembrance of the high stature and high subjection of Hynap with his afzunlig'i bila." This chapter states the following: "O child, Know that a person without skill is always useless and does not benefit anyone. You know that a thorn bush has flesh but no shade. A person without skill is just like a thorn bush, and benefits neither himself nor others.

"No matter how high a lineage a person may have, if he does not have a craft, he will despair of the honor and respect of the people."

The author says that one should not be ashamed or neglectful of learning a craft. Because only then can one be protected from feeling ashamed, embarrassed, and regretful." See the little crafts of the people, and learn the truth well. If you can get a good horse and good food from ignorance and stupidity, be ignorant and stupid, if not, learn a craft. Do not be ashamed to learn and listen, so that you will be free from embarrassment and regret."

In the chapter in question, the thinker also explains the concept of "artisan". According to Kaykovus, "a skilled person is a person who, knowing that his dignity and rank are higher than others due to virtue and skill, strives for virtue and skill more than before and becomes more noble and skilled than before. Anyone who does this will quickly become dear and great among the people. So, if a person who knows this, uses virtue and skill, this is a sign of foolishness."

Crafts flourished in the Middle Ages. The result of this can also be assessed by the situation at the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries. After the colonization of Central Asia by Tsarist Russia - "during the first census in 1897, it was known that the majority of the population in large cities was made up of craftsmen. For example, 64 percent of the population of Namangan city, 52 percent of the population of Kokand city, 54 percent of the city of Chust, 50 percent of the city of Margilan, 45 percent of the city of Andijan, and 29 percent of the population of Tashkent and Samarkand cities were considered craftsmen."

Examples of this include wood carving and painting used in national architectural monuments, as well as striking examples of blacksmithing widely used in social and domestic life. "In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Uzbek blacksmithing developed so much that independent sectors emerged within it based on the division of labor. For example, the Uzbek knife, which was considered a household item and a part of the male wardrobe, was made by special knifemakers, locks and keys were made by locksmiths or locksmiths, needles and bigizs were made by needlemakers or needlemakers, various tools and items were made by blacksmiths such as locksmiths, nailers, farriers, and shoemakers. Local blacksmiths knew about 40 types of tools. In Bukhara, there was a known industry that produced 32 types of iron products. Coppersmithing was also very widespread. For example, at the beginning of our century, there were about 400 coppersmiths in Bukhara and more than 200 in Khiva. Some masters skillfully made artistic objects. The coppersmiths of Bukhara, Fergana, and Khiva were especially famous.

They produced various drinking vessels, food and milk vessels (copper lagan, copper plate, copper barkash, lali, copper jug, khumcha, kumgan, stoyil, aftoba, obdasta, tas, lagan, solobcha, chilobchin, koshtul), various boxes and chests, nasvoy vessels, etc. Many items were given embossed or carved patterns. After the Russian conquest of the khanates, local coppersmiths began to produce their own samovars.

Coppersmiths mainly brought raw materials from Russia, zinc, lead, acid, and sodium nitrate were also imported from abroad. All sources speak of the excellent craftsmanship of local craftsmen in making artistic objects.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

The steady development of national crafts continued in the first two decades of the last century. Due to the change in the socio-political system, the emergence of intolerance for any form of nationality under the idea of internationalism, a long-term crisis was observed in the development of the industry, while some types of national crafts were produced in a narrow range, while others (for example, cradle-making) were strictly prohibited.

“In Central Asia, all types of crafts were preserved until the 20s of the 20th century. Crafts played a major role in the production relations of cities such as Bukhara, Samarkand, Kokand, Khiva, Tashkent (for example, in the 60s of the 19th century, 27 types of crafts developed in Khiva, there were 556 shops of craftsmen in the city's markets, and in the 80s, 2,528 households were engaged in handicrafts in the city); “In the city of Tashkent alone, in 1870, about 775 weaving workshops operated.”

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